

INTERACTION OF AROMATIC HYDROXY KETONES AND THIONYL
CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF FINELY DIVIDED COPPER. PART XI.
PREPARATION OF 2:2'-DIHYDROXY-3:3'-DIACETYL- AND
-3:3'-DIPROPIONYL-5:5'-DIMETHYLDIPHENYL SULPHIDES
AND 2:2'-DIHYDROXY-3:3'-DIMETHYL-5:5'-
DIACETYLDIPHENYL SULPHIDE

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Preparation of 2:2'-dihydroxy-3:3'-diacetyl-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide (I), 2:2'-dihydroxy-3:3'-dipropionyl-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide (II) and 2:2'-dihydroxy-3:3'-dimethyl-5:5'-diacetyldiphenyl sulphide (III) is described. The constitution of these sulphides has been arrived at by their interaction with nitric acid and identifying the products obtained. Their acetyl and 2:4-dinitrophenyl-hydrazone derivative have been prepared.

Present work is the continuation of the work published previously (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 266, 519). The sulphides (I), (II) and (III) are obtained when 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (2-acetyl-*p*-cresol, OH=1) 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propionophenone (2-propionyl-*p*-cresol) and 3-methyl-4-hydroxyacetophenone (4-acetyl-*o*-cresol) respectively are treated with thionyl chloride in presence of finely divided copper or with sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride.

Action of nitric acid on (I) affords 2-nitro-6-acetyl-*p*-cresol (2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone) as proved by mixed melting point with the nitration product of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone. It is therefore assigned the constitution 2:2'-dihydroxy-3:3'-diacetyl-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide.

Sulphide (II), however, furnishes 2:6-dinitro-*p*-cresol (-OH=1) by the action of nitric acid in presence of sulphuric acid. Nitro group in position-6 has come in place of the propionyl group and the other nitro group must have come in place of the sulphur atom joining the two nuclei. It is therefore assigned the constitution 2:2'-dihydroxy-3:3'-dipropionyl-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl sulphide.

Sulphide (III) furnishes 4:6-dinitro-*o*-cresol (-OH=1) by the action of nitric acid in presence of sulphuric acid. Nitro group in position-4 has come in place of the acetyl group and the other nitro group must have come in place of the sulphur atom linking the two nuclei. It is therefore designated as 2:2'-dihydroxy-3:3'-dimethyl-5:5'-diacetyldiphenyl sulphide. Diacetyl and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives of these disulphides have been prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-diacetyl-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl Sulphide (I).—Copper powder (2 g.) was slowly added (over 2 hours) to the mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (2 g.) and thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) (E. Merck) and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted with dry benzene and

filtered. The paste, obtained after removal of the liquid, was subjected to the action of steam for about half an hour, when it solidified to a yellowish powder. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 100° (decomp.), yield 0.5 g.

It is soluble in benzene, acetone and carbon disulphide and insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, ether and acetic acid. (Found: C, 65.26; H, 5.69; S, 10.14. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4S$ requires C, 65.46; H, 5.45; S, 9.69 per cent).

The same sulphide was also obtained when 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (2 g.) was treated with sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride (2 c.c.) and allowed the reaction to proceed overnight at room temperature. Next day it was washed with dry ether to remove sulphur chloride and the paste remaining behind was subjected to the action of steam for about half an hour, when it solidified. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 100° (decomp.), yield 1 g. It showed no lowering in melting point with the above sulphide.

The *diacetyl derivative* of (I) was prepared by boiling it for 2 hours with acetic anhydride and pyridine. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $77-78^{\circ}$. (Found: S, 7.8. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4S$ requires S, 7.7 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (I) crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. $175-76^{\circ}$. (Found: S, 4.7. $C_{20}H_{12}O_6N_2S$ requires S, 4.60 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-methylacetophenone (2-nitro-6-acetyl-p-cresol).—The sulphide (I:1 g.) was added to HNO_3 (conc., 20 c.c.) and the mixture was warmed on a boiling water-bath for about 1 hour, when a yellowish substance separated. The mixture was then diluted with water and the product obtained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $130-31^{\circ}$. It contained nitrogen but no sulphur. It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with an authentic specimen of 2-nitro-6-acetyl-*p*-cresol, prepared according to Bredereck *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1939, 72B, 1414).

2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-dipropionyl-5:5'-dimethyldiphenyl Sulphide (II).—Copper powder (2 g.) was gradually added to the mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropio-phenone (3 c.c.) and thiouyl chloride (Pure, Merck, 5 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed on a boiling water-bath for about 3 hours. The mixture was then extracted with chloroform. The brownish paste left after removal of the solvent turned into a yellow solid on treatment with alcohol. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 110° , yield 2 g. (Found: C, 67.01; H, 6.16; S, 9.07. $C_{20}H_{22}O_4S$ requires C, 67.03; H, 6.14; S, 8.94 per cent).

It is insoluble in alcohol and acetic acid, fairly soluble in acetone, ether and benzene, and easily in chloroform and carbon disulphide.

The same sulphide was obtained by heating the mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propio-phenone (3 c.c.), sulphur monochloride or dichloride (2 c.c.) and copper powder (0.5 g.) on a boiling water-bath for 3 hours. The mixture was then extracted with dry chloroform. The reddish paste remaining behind after removal of chloroform was repeatedly washed with alcohol and then boiled with acetic acid and finally washed with water and left in water for some time, when it solidified. It crystallised from benzene, m.p. 110° , yield 0.5 g.

It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with the above sulphide.

Diacetyl derivative of (II) was prepared by heating it with acetic anhydride in presence of pyridine and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 101-102°. (Found: S, 7.01. $C_{24}H_{20}O_6S$ requires S, 7.24 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (II) crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 200-201°. (Found: S, 4.87. $C_{12}H_{10}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.56 per cent).

2:6-Dinitro-p-cresol.—The sulphide (II: 1 g.) was suspended in H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 c.c.) and HNO_3 (conc., 15 c.c.) was added to it, when the substance went into a yellow solution, giving out the smell of propionic acid. It was left overnight at room temperature and then diluted. The solution was extracted with ether, when a yellow solid was obtained. It contained nitrogen and no sulphur. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 80-81°. (Found: N, 13.9. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_5N_2$: N, 14.14 per cent). It did not show any lowering in melting point when mixed with an authentic specimen prepared according to Friache (*Annalen*, 1884, 224, 138).

2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-dimethyl-5:5'-diacetyldiphenyl Sulphide (III).—3-Methyl-4-hydroxyacetophenone (2 g.) was mixed with thionyl chloride (3 c.c.), and copper powder (1 g.) was added in small quantities at a time (over 1 hour). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then extracted with dry ether. The brown paste left after removal of ether was repeatedly boiled with water when ultimately it solidified. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 98-99° (decomp.), yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 65.31; H, 5.62; S, 9.69. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 65.45; H, 5.45; S, 9.69 per cent).

The same sulphide was obtained by the action of sulphur monochloride or dichloride (3 c.c.) on 3-methyl-4-hydroxyacetophenone (2 g.) at room temperature and allowing the reaction to proceed overnight. It was worked up as in the case of the previous experiment. It showed no lowering in melting point with the sulphide (III).

The *diacetyl derivative* of (III) was prepared as in the case of (I) and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 112°. (Found: S, 8.01. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6S$ requires S, 7.7 per cent).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (III) crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 158-59°. (Found: S, 4.57. $C_{30}H_{20}O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 4.63 per cent).

4:6-Dinitro-o-cresol.—The sulphide (III: 1 g.) was suspended in H_2SO_4 (conc., 20 c.c.) and HNO_3 (conc., 15 c.c.) was added to it. The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for about half an hour, left overnight at room temperature, and then diluted with water. The resulting solution was extracted with ether when a yellowish solid was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 86-87°. It contained nitrogen but no sulphur. (Found: N, 14.3. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_5N_2$: N, 14.4 per cent).

It showed no lowering in melting point when mixed with an authentic specimen prepared according to Rapp (*Annalen*, 1884, 224, 175).